

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan

Deliverable 7.2

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WP Co-Leader(s)	Jacob Carstensen, Miguel Costa Leal
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Authors	Miguel Costa Leal, Alice Estrela, Joana Marques, Marta Leal, Paulo Salvador, Angel Borja, Henn Ojaveer, Hege Gundersen, Giorgio Santinelli, Rowana Walton, Jacob Carstensen
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1. Deliverable 7.2 Overview

This document delineates the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) goals of OBAMA-NEXT. It describes the DEC strategy to reach the different target audiences of the project, and how the different key outputs, tools, and materials developed in OBAMA-NEXT will be used to maximize the impact of the project. In addition, a work plan and methods for tracking the progress and achievement of DEC activities.

The DEC Plan was designed following the recommendations made by the European Commission (EC) for the appropriate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication of Horizon Europe projects (i.e. Horizon Europe Participant Portal Online Manual, Communicating EU Research & Innovation Guide). Accordingly, the DEC activities aim and contribute to maximise the impact of Research & Innovation (R&I) actions. DEC activities are differentiated based on the objectives, focus and target groups (Table 1).

Table 1. Differences among Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation according to the EC.

	COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
Focus	About project activities and results	About results	About results
Objective	Inform and reach out to society, show the benefits of research	Transfer knowledge and results. Enable the use and uptake of results (Open Science)	Best efforts to exploit the owned results, or to have them exploited by another legal entity
Target audience	Multiple audiences (citizens, media, stakeholders, etc.)	Audiences that might use results (scientists, industry, professional organizations, policymakers, ...)	Organizations that are making concrete use of results (researchers, industry, authorities, policymakers, ...)
Timeline	From the start of the action until the end	When results are available	When results are available and up to 4 years after the project ended

It is worth noting that the partners assume a series of obligations related to communication, dissemination and exploitation when signing the EC Grant Agreement, which are:

- Communicate and promote the action and its results (Art 17.1 of the GA);
- Disseminate results (Art 17.1 of the GA);
- Ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) (Art 17 of the GA);
- Take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of the results — up to four years after the end of the project – by using them in further research activities; developing, creating, or marketing a product, process or service (Art 17 of the GA);
- Acknowledge EU funding in all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results financed by the action by using the wording and criteria specified in the Grant Agreement (Article 17.2).

In this view, this deliverable is structured as follows:

- Framework – defines and explains the DEC framework that was used to develop a DEC strategy and workplan, and how it will contribute to reach OBAMA-NEXT specific objectives;
- Strategy – explains how the DEC framework is used to define a strategy to promote the communication, dissemination, and exploitation of OBAMA-NEXT results and outputs;
- Workplan – a detailed description of the tasks implementing the DEC plan and its expected progress throughout the duration of OBAMA-NEXT;
- Impact – identifies and quantifies Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of the DEC activities of OBAMA-NEXT.

2. DEC Framework

This framework aims to facilitate the development of a DEC strategy and the subsequent implementation of the workplan to achieve the impact goals of the OBAMA-NEXT project. It provides information on how partners can work individually and collectively in maximizing the impact of the DEC actions. Concomitantly, orientations are also provided to ensure the long-term sustainability and exploitation of the OBAMA-NEXT materials, results, and developed tools, which greatly rely on establishing connections and synergies among project partners and between partners and stakeholders.

The DEC framework considers the cross-disciplinary scope of the OBAMA-NEXT project, which covers social sciences, conservation and management, policy, ecology, biodiversity, fisheries, earth observation, sensor technologies, governance, oceanography, mathematics, software development, and data management, among others. The framework also considers relevant national and regional specificities, together with existing resources in the partners' institutions, to maximize the impact of DEC activities and ensure the visibility of OBAMA-NEXT activities, at least, throughout Europe.

2.1. Lasswell communication model in OBAMA-NEXT

A Lasswell communication model has been applied to the OBAMA-NEXT to develop the DEC plan. With the ultimate goal of achieving an effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication, this model involves addressing **who** is producing information regarding **what** outcomes, to **whom** is the information is being conveyed, **where** are the activities going to be carried out, and ultimately **why** are the activities being carried out. This is a summary of how the Lasswell communication model is applied to the OBAMA-NEXT DEC activities:

- WHO
 - OBAMA-NEXT is a consortium, i.e. group of institutions who will produce results and tools to be disseminated, exploited and communicated;
- WHAT
 - Approximate science to policy, schools and general audience;
 - Promote ocean literacy;
 - Promote the potential of technology;
 - Raise Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) on emerging technology;
 - Train scientists and stakeholders on the use of the developed products;
 - Disseminate scientific outputs to peers;
 - Establish and maintain good communication with other H2020/Horizon Europe projects;
 - Maximise the impact of the results;
 - Ensure accurate and efficient internal communication;
- TO WHOM
 - Scientific community;
 - Project partners;
 - Programme partners;

- Policy makers and policy advisers;
- Managers;
- International organizations;
- General audience;
- Teachers and students;
- **WHERE**
 - Popular articles for students and schools;
 - Digital and print materials;
 - Educational modules;
 - In-person and remote meetings and workshops;
 - International and open-access data bases for data, algorithms, code, and software;
 - Scientific publications and conferences;
 - Summer schools;
 - Policy briefs;
 - Website and social media.
- **WHY**
 - Disseminate OBAMA-NEXT results to diverse audiences to maximize impact of the action;
 - Integrate OBAMA-NEXT outputs into biodiversity observation, mapping, and monitoring;
 - Create impact of OBAMA-NEXT on the scientific community and expert users of the developed technology.

2.1.1. WHO

Following the Lasswell communication model, we have identified OBAMA-NEXT as the entity who will carry out the DEC activities, i.e. the group of institutions directly involved in the development of OBAMA-NEXT activities. In particular:

- **Researchers**

The research community of OBAMA-NEXT, in particular the researchers of the different partner institutions, play a key role in the DEC activities, especially in regard to dissemination and exploitation activities targeting fellow experts. Some members of the OBAMA-NEXT research community are also experts in communicating scientific results to other audiences, such as policy makers, policy advisers, and managers, and will be active contributors to such communication activities. OBAMA-NEXT is also relying on the members of the Practitioners Advisory Board (PAB) and partners and associated partners of the project to contribute to communication of the scientific results and outputs of the project to other audiences.

- **Practitioners Advisory Board**

The PAB of OBAMA-NEXT was established to ensure a direct contact with key stakeholders, such as the national authorities from EU member states implementing the WFD, MSFD, and BHD, and reporting for the biodiversity strategy, as well as RSC authorities, the EEA, and DG-ENV. The PAB members not only represent some of these stakeholders, but they are also involved in the development of OBAMA-NEXT by providing key inputs and by externalizing outputs.

- **Outreach experts**

Science Crunchers is a scientific creative agency specialized in science communication and is among the OBAMA-NEXT partners, particularly as co-lead of WP7 and in charge of the outreach tasks. This partner, in collaboration with the research community of OBAMA-NEXT, will actively contribute to make the science of this easily understandable for the general audience.

2.1.2. WHAT

OBAMA-NEXT focuses on complex, advanced, and innovative technologies for monitoring of marine and coastal ecosystems. In addition to communicate the project results and outputs, the communication activities will focus on the fundamental topics covered by the project, such as:

- Technologies for ocean observation (pelagic and benthic environments);
- Computational advances for data processing and visualization ;
- Novel techniques and approaches for the assessment of ecological patterns;
- Relevance of applications of next-generation tools in marine biodiversity for developing/advancing policies and management frameworks.

2.1.3. WHOM

OBAMA-NEXT DEC activities will focus on the following four stakeholder groups:

- Key targets
 - One of the main target groups of OBAMA-NEXT include national authorities from EU member states implementing the WFD, MSFD, and BHD, and reporting for the Biodiversity Strategy, as well as authorities associated with the Regional Sea Conventions (RSCs), the European Environmental Agency (EEA), Directorate General for Environment (DG-ENV), and the Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBD);
- Scientific community
 - OBAMA-NEXT will produce results and tools by the scientific community and also to this community, particular, scientists working on biodiversity, including predictive models. A key audience are the project partners, which integrates 22 institutions and, approximately, 120 scientists. In addition, such partner institutions create a network of scientific projects and collaborators with whom the results will be shared and disseminated, including ACTNOW, EuropaBON, GES4SEAS, MarinePLAN, Marine SABRES, MARBEFES, MARCO-BOLO, MPA-EUROPE, BIOCEAN5D, DOORS, among others. Such large network of scientists is a primary target for the dissemination and exploitation of the OBAMA-NEXT outputs;
- International organisations and end-users
 - Other key stakeholders are international organizations focused on biological data collection (e.g., GOOS, MBON, GEOSS, ESA, KCBD), data organization and display tools (e.g., OBIS, GBIF). In addition, consultancies that provide services relating to biodiversity are also expected to use and benefit from OBAMA-NEXT results. Lastly, end-users in non-European Regional Seas Conventions, such as countries with Ocean Acts (e.g., USA, Canada, Australia) are also going to be targeted by DEC activities;
- General society

- The general audience is always a stakeholder group of any research and innovation action funded by the European Commission. Not only this group plays a key role on the decisions that policymakers make, but it also needs to be engaged in ocean literacy activities. Particular attention will also be given to young generations and educators through their engagement in several communication and dissemination tasks.

2.1.4. WHERE

Different tools and channels will be used for DEC actions depending on the main outcomes, expected effect, and purpose of the task, such as digital media, publications, and training.

Digital media

The OBAMA-NEXT website (Figure 1), available at <https://obama-next.eu/>, is the main anchor for the project DEC activities, which will serve all audiences and a repository of information or channel to inform the whereabouts of the main DEC products. In particular, the sections “Resources” and “News” will be regularly updated with the most recent outputs, achievements, and events.

The main contents of the website will be maintained by the project coordinator after the end of the project, either by migrating it to the website of the project coordinator or outreach coordinator, or by keeping the current OBAMA-NEXT website live for at least four additional years. This will contribute to maximize the impact of the project.

Figure 1. OBAMA-NEXT website landing page.

Several short videos will be produced including a logo reveal, an explainer of the project, short interviews (Figure 2) with key researchers of the project, as well as animated videos focusing on the main topics of the project.

Figure 2. Screenshot of a video interview of OBAMA-NEXT coordinator.

Infographics will be produced to convey important messages associated with OBAMA-NEXT as well as to communicate and disseminate key results and outputs (Figure 3). For instance, infographics will be produced to explain the work of different WPs, as well as graphical abstracts to maximize the impact of scientific publications (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Infographic produced to summarize the OBAMA-NEXT project and workflow.

Figure 4. Infographic produced to submit as a graphical abstract of a scientific publication (in preparation).

Various social media channels were activated for OBAMA-NEXT (Twitter, LinkedIn, and Youtube). The social media channels will be used for communicating and disseminating results of the project, and in particular to share infographics and videos. The number of followers/subscribers and engagement will be regularly monitored, as well as comments from viewers. In addition, all social media posts will use the #OBAMANEXT. With this hashtag, partners and individuals can contribute to the social media of the project, as well as take advantage of the already existing networks of individuals and partner institutions, thereby maximizing the impact of and engagement in the OBAMA-NEXT.

Publications

OBAMA-NEXT will contribute to the scientific literature by publishing peer-reviewed papers and chapters, thereby contributing to disseminate the project results to the scientific community, competent authorities, ocean and biodiversity managers, and policymakers. Open-access (OA) publications will be encouraged as Gold OA, but Green OA publication will also be possible, by including the last accepted version of the manuscript in the Zenodo repository created for OBAMA-NEXT (<http://zenodo.org/communities/obama-next/>).

The partners involved in OBAMA-NEXT will participate in international conferences, exhibitions, and webinars to disseminate the project activities and results. The project will also be promoted in local and regional events hosted by different partner organizations. Joint special sessions will also be actively promoted with other projects under similar calls, and in particular with the sister project MARCO-BOLO, with whom a very close communication and collaboration has already been established.

Policy briefs will be produced within the scope of WPs 1, 2, 3 and 6, and disseminated to different stakeholders, at national, regional, and European level. Particular emphasis will be given to those included in the PAB of OBAMA-NEXT, national authorities from EU member states implementing the WFD, MSFD, and BHD, and reporting for the Biodiversity Strategy, as well as authorities associated with RSCs, the EEA, DG-ENV, and the

KCBD. A white paper merging the information detailed in the policy briefs will be compiled and complemented with orientation principles and key take home messages from all other WPs.

Ocean literacy is vital in our current society and also a focus activity within the OBAMA-NEXT DEC strategy. In this view, an educational activity will be prepared with selected Blue Schools from different European countries represented by partner institutions of this action. Researchers from the different organizations of OBAMA-NEXT together with Science Crunchers will write short articles with tailored illustrations. The articles will then be reviewed by young students from the selected schools to comment on its clarity, topics and wording that need to be better explained, and concepts that deserve better explanation for the target audience. Upon receiving the feedback from the students and teachers, OBAMA-NEXT researchers will revise and finalize the article. A set of articles will be produced by different partners from different countries in the different local languages. All articles will be translated to the different languages involved in this activity and combined in a digital book that will be made available in the project website, to the schools, students and educators involved in the activity, as well as in ocean literacy platforms (e.g. EuroGOOS).

Training

The OBAMA-NEXT partners commit to train at least 15 PhD and postdocs who will have the skills to exploit and apply innovative products to be developed. Not only will these trained young researchers exploit the results during the lifetime of the project, but they can also promote a long-term exploitation throughout their professional careers in the private and public sector, universities and research institutes.

OBAMA-NEXT will contribute to summer schools targeting early career researchers. The summer schools will focus on topics associated with the activities of OBAMA-NEXT and will involve lecturers from different partner institutions (and respecting social responsibility principles) and include sessions with keynote speakers, as well as practical sessions, poster presentations, and a discussion session. The summer school will be hosted and organized by Dr Angel Borja from AZTI (OBAMA-NEXT WP1 co-leader, and GES4SEAS project coordinator). For instance, the 2023 summer school is organized in the framework of several Horizon Europe projects (GES4SEAS, OBAMA-NEXT, BIOcean5D, ACTNOW, and MARBEFES) and will focus on “Innovative and practical tools for monitoring and assessing multiple human pressures affecting biodiversity in marine systems” (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Poster of the summer school organized for 2023.

To ensure the exploitation of results and products, a set of materials derived from the different scientific and communication tasks will be merged into the form of educational modules, which will be exploited through online platforms with which OBAMA-NEXT partners are already engaged, such as EuroGOOS, REDUCAMAR, and the Ocean Teacher Global Academy (IOC-UNESCO). These actions will help increase ocean literacy and promote the long-term exploitation of the products developed throughout the OBAMA-NEXT.

Physical and remote courses and a final ‘tailor-made’ seminar will be organised in WP1 (and in collaboration with WP4, WP5 and WP7) with technical and scientific contents prepared to train stakeholders and key end-users on the contents of the toolbox. These initiatives will facilitate the use of the outputs and exploitation of OBAMA-NEXT results and outcomes, both during and after the project.

Documentation

An online repository will host a collection of novel models and methods, to ensure that all tools developed within OBAMA-NEXT project. Next to the tools for visualization, advanced statistics and artificial intelligence, the partners co-developing the toolbox take part in writing comprehensive code documentation, describing test reproducibility and usability. A combination of pictures, schematics, diagrams, textual explanation and expected outputs will be placed next to the tools, using GitHub or possibly other similar online open platforms. Technical requirements, range of applicability and uncertainties will be documented as well. Researchers, scientific

community, and policy makers who are interested in the use, processing or end-results will have access to the platform.

3. DEC Strategy

Considering the DEC framework described in the previous section, a DEC strategy has been defined taking into consideration the different outputs of the project, DEC tools, and target audience. Table 2 shows a summary on the tools that will be used to meet the different DEC goals, and what are the expected outcomes.

Table 2. Contribution of the different tools to the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of the OBAMA-NEXT.

	Objective	Tools	Expected outcomes
Dissemination	Maximising impact of OBAMA-NEXT on the scientific community and expert-users. Transfer knowledge and results to enable their use and uptake in real life. Make scientific results a common good.	Website, social media, policy briefs, white paper, peer-reviewed publications, participation at conferences, summer schools, individual communications	Raise awareness of the scientific outputs to peers. Approximate science to policy, to international organizations and to key stakeholders.
Exploitation	Increase TRL of existing technologies through testing, validation, and applicability demonstration. Actively train scientists and key stakeholders to use and integrate results into research, policy, and monitoring practices.	Physical and remote courses, seminars, educational modules, datasets and algorithms.	Promote the integration and application of results and tools into future research practices, policy and management frameworks.
Communication	Ensure and accurate external communication that informs diverse audiences, including the society. Raise awareness of how public money is spend and show the success of EU collaborations.	Website, social media, infographics, videos, articles for children	Promote ocean literacy. Increase the visibility of OBAMA-NEXT to promote scientific progress.

3.1. Dissemination

The Dissemination strategy aims at maximising impact of the OBAMA-NEXT project, its results, and outputs, in the scientific community and expert-users through a set of custom-made actions (e.g. policy briefs, white paper, digital communications, and scientific publications).

OBAMA-NEXT has established the PAB to bridge the gap between science and the key stakeholders, including policy makers. The PAB members will be actively involved throughout the duration of the project, particularly through participating in dedicated workshops, as well as guaranteeing that the policy briefs that will be prepared address their needs and match their expectations as key stakeholders. In addition, guidance documents on the

use of OBAMA-NEXT outputs and toolbox will be prepared for this audience, which will be followed by training actions (see exploitation section below) and dedicated seminars.

Scientific outputs, particularly peer-reviewed publications and presentations in international conferences, will be produced to support the information to be disseminated to stakeholders. Such publications will be open access and assembled in publicly available repositories, such as a Zenodo community (<http://zenodo.org/communities/obama-next/>), where all publications, datasets, software, etc. will be available open access. In addition, all public deliverables will be available in the project's website, and shared to a mass audience through social media.

Summer schools will contribute to the education and training of early career researchers, managers from European, national and local administrations, researchers and members of NGOs and conservation organizations on key topics of OBAMA-NEXT. Such summer schools are hosted in San Sebastian (Spain) and organized by Dr Angel Borja (AZTI) who is co-lead of WP1 and coordinator of the GES4SEAS project. These summer schools take place every year since 2004, and OBAMA-NEXT will participate and actively contribute towards its success. Not only this contributes to explore synergies between, at least, two Horizon Europe projects (GES4SEAS and OBAMA-NEXT), but this also actively contributes to the training of future scientists working in marine biodiversity and coastal management. These synergies can be found in the fact that OBAMA-NEXT focus mainly in monitoring and GES4SEAS in assessing marine ecosystems, and especially biodiversity.

To increase the potential of OBAMA-NEXT dissemination, joint activities with international initiatives will be led by WP leads. These will include cooperation with the KCBD, MBPN, EuroGOOS, ROOSes, IPBES, IUC, IOC-UN, among others. In addition, dissemination and cooperation activities will be implemented with the UN Decade of the Oceans. Links will be established with other EU projects, in particular the sister project MARCO-BOLO, and networks of excellence. Such activities will be promoted through:

- Inviting project/initiative coordinators to our annual meetings.
- Organizing joint special sessions in international conferences to stimulate exchange of information around marine biodiversity.
- Organizing a joint annual meetings and/or final conference.

3.2. Exploitation

OBAMA-NEXT ultimately aims to the integration of its main products into ocean policy and their use by other users (i.e., scientist, key stakeholders, international organizations and consultancies). In this view, training sessions, educational modules and open access datasets and software will facilitate the exploitation of results.

OBAMA-NEXT will be deeply engaged in training the next generation of researchers in marine biodiversity monitoring and mapping technologies, particularly PhD and postdocs to exploit the results during the lifetime of the project and beyond throughout their professional careers in the private and public sector, universities and research institutes. These trained young researchers can be employed in the future in the private and public sector, universities and research institutes, thereby contributing to further develop and exploit these tools.

Another important asset of OBAMA-NEXT relates to the ability to assess the potential of new technologies for producing effective and regular ecosystem and biodiversity information. This project will help provide references on how to overcome potential barriers that might arise against the practical implementation of new technology in monitoring programmes. OBAMA-NEXT will contribute to raise the TRL of several technologies, even though it will not specifically develop any hardware technology. Through testing, validation, and applicability demonstration of relevant tools in marine environments, OBAMA-NEXT will allow for emerging technologies to be raised from a TRL 2-3 to a TLR 4-6. This will be demonstrated through the application of data from selected LSs (WP5) and through demonstrating the applicability and utility of the information products to support policy implementation (WP6).

OBAMA-NEXT will deliver algorithms for data products that will be established in close dialogue and consultation with stakeholders. All data and algorithms will be open access through EMODnet and other public repositories, and the tools will also be accessible in open software and code repositories for future development and exploitation. This will provide a set of tools that will be possible to apply across all European coastal seas, without the need for local configurations. In this context, OBAMA-NEXT will help convert raw technology-produced data into biologically meaningful information. This democratisation of technology will not only help collaborations between different projects (e.g., GES4SEAS) become much easier, but it will also create the potential for collaborating projects to achieve higher TRLs. Lastly, the long-term impacts of OBAMA-NEXT will be promoted by submitting the developed tools to organisations such as ICES, EMODnet, and GBIF, and utilizing the information products for teaching and reporting by the RSCs.

Another objective of this project is to promote the development of protocols for applications of eDNA. OBAMA-NEXT will translate the applications of eDNA from being purely academic into having multiple uses in applied science, thus ensuring the most comprehensive use of all collectable data. OBAMA-NEXT will also play an important role in combining new and old tools, as it will help assess the quality of new data streams from sensor-based techniques and mix their use with more traditional tools. This combination will help recover information on marine biodiversity changes over large spatial and temporal scales, thus improving marine monitoring programmes. Therefore, by contributing with validated and integrated tools for biodiversity observation and mapping, OBAMA-NEXT will help shape the future of marine monitoring.

To ensure the exploitation of results and products, a set of materials derived from the different scientific and communication tasks will be merged into the form of five educational modules that will be disseminated through web-based platforms, such as the OceanTeacher Global Academy (IOC-UNESCO) and the Ocean Literacy platform of European Global Ocean Observing System (EuroGOOS). These actions will help increase ocean literacy and promote the long-term exploitation of the products developed throughout OBAMA-NEXT.

Physical and remote courses and a final ‘tailor-made’ seminar will be organised in WP1 (and in collaboration with WP4, WP5 and WP7) with technical and scientific contents prepared to train stakeholders and key end-users on the contents of the toolbox. These initiatives will facilitate the use of the outputs and exploitation of OBAMA-NEXT results and outcomes, both during and after the project.

3.3. Communication

The Communication Strategy of OBAMA-NEXT is developed to increase the visibility of the project to the wider audience and, ultimately, to promote ocean literacy.

Branding and communication actions activities (WP7) have been carried out to develop the visual identity of OBAMA-NEXT, which includes the project logo, collection of visual elements, as well as a brand book with all the defined guidelines for a consistent and coherent application of the brand to be used by all partners. In addition, the project website has been created (www.obama-next.eu) as well as the relevant social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube). This increases the proximity between the project and different audiences, promoting communication and thus optimising the project's impact on the scientific community, society, and media.

Organic content will be created to communicate the project, the core scientific involved in OBAMA-NEXT, as well as the project's results. In particular, at least 20 infographics and 10 short videos will be produced to maximize engagement and facilitate the project's communication to a wider and global audience.

Early career scientists from different partner organisations will also write dissemination articles to promote ocean literacy activities in schools and maximise engagement with young generations. The writing process will be performed in collaboration with Science Crunchers, which is familiar in communicating to young generations, and supervised by project experts. All articles will be illustrated by the Science Crunchers design team, thus also promoting a bridge between science and art activities in schools. At least five dissemination articles will be written, which will be then peer-reviewed by young students (age groups to be decided with each school) from different schools within the Network of European Blue Schools. The final step is the translation of the articles into different languages to help maximise the engagement with youngsters from different countries and the international impact of dissemination activities. The articles will be disseminated on the OBAMA-NEXT website, EuroGOOS, and through other web portal on ocean literacy that might be created throughout the duration of the project. This activity will ultimately contribute to bridge the gap between science and society, and especially with schools, educators, and children.

4. DEC plan step-by-step

The DEC activities are described in WP7, together with project management, and include the following tasks:

- Task 7.3. Branding, DEC plans and coordination of external communication/dissemination.
- Task 7.6. Engage with other relevant scientific projects and networks.
- Task 7.7. Educational activities and tools.

1.1. Task 7.3 Branding, DEC plans and coordination of external communication/dissemination

The current document corresponds to the DEC plan of OBAMA-NEXT, which will be updated as the project progresses. At the end of the project the performance of the DEC activities and their impact will be evaluated.

In order to maintain track of the DEC activities implemented by all partners, an Excel template has been created, which will be completed on a regular basis. This Excel file aims to compile the different DEC actions led by the different partners, the target audiences, the number of people receiving the DEC action, among other information.

The visual identity of the project has also been developed, including a logo (Figure 6), iconography (Figure 7), a set of visual elements, a brand book (Figure 8) with guidelines for the branding, as well as PowerPoint and Word templates (Figure 9) for a consistent use of the OBAMA-NEXT brand by all partners and for all DEC activities. A template for scientific posters has also been prepared for a consistent dissemination of the project's results in scientific conferences (Figure 10). It is also important to highlight that, as required per Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement, all material used for communication and dissemination purposes of OBAMA-NEXT, will demonstrate the EU emblem along with the respective grant agreement number.

Figure 6. OBAMA-NEXT logo in its different versions (full colour, black, and white).

Figure 7. Example of iconography developed for OBAMA-NEXT.

Figure 8. Cover of the OBAMA-NEXT brand book .

Figure 9. Cover of the Word template for OBAMA-NEXT deliverables.

Figure 10. Template for the OBAMA-NEXT scientific poster template.

The accounts for different social media channels were created:

- Twitter (<https://twitter.com/ObamaNext>)
- LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/obama-next-project-848927260/>)
- Youtube (<https://www.youtube.com/@obama-next/>)

Within the scope of this task, at least 20 infographics and at least 10 short videos will be produced. For instance, a video explaining the project has already been published on the OBAMA-NEXT YouTube channel (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Explainer video about the OBAMA-NEXT project.

A total of four policy briefs will be produced within the scope of WPs 1, 2, 3 and 6. The policy briefs will be disseminated to different stakeholders, at national, regional, and European level. A white paper merging the information detailed in the policy briefs will be produced, which will allow for all available information to be presented in one single document, to then be consulted by key stakeholders and partners alike towards the end of the project.

1.2. Task 7.6. Engage with other relevant scientific projects and networks

This task will contribute to make OBAMA-NEXT visible to other ongoing EU projects (e.g., GES4SEAS, EUROPABON, FutureMARES; JERICO S3/JERICO RI, EMODnet, European Topic Centers) or in this call (e.g., BIOcen5D, MARBEFES, MARCO-BOLO, Marine SABRES, MSP4BIO, MARinePlan, MPA Europe) and organisations (EEA, JRC, ICES, RSC, etc.). This will be achieved by organizing joint coordination meetings, at least once per year, with a final joint meeting. Cooperation through the international members of the PAB and engagement with international platforms on marine data (e.g., OBIS, GBIF, among others) and ocean literacy (e.g., EuroGOOS, IOC-OTGA) is already established and will be strengthened.

Engagement with the Atlantic Initiatives will be promoted through, at least, participation on the AANChOR action (All-Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and Innovation). In addition, the OBAMA-NEXT project has already been featured in the EuropaBON newsletter from January 2023. The participation in newsletters from this and other networks and organizations will also be promoted. Lastly, this task will promote and coordinate cooperation with the UN Decade of the Oceans initiatives through members of the consortium.

1.3. Task 7.7. Educational activities and tools

An educational activity will be prepared with selected schools from different European countries represented by partner institutions of this action. Researchers from the different organizations of OBAMA-NEXT together with Science Crunchers will write at least five short articles (1000 to 2000 words) with custom-made illustrations. After being commented by young students and teachers from the selected schools (age groups to be discussed individually with each school), OBAMA-NEXT researchers will revise and finalize the article. The articles will be translated into different languages and combined in a digital book, which will be available in the project's website and in ocean literacy platforms (e.g. EuroGOOS), and shared with the schools, educators, and students and their parents.

OBAMA-NEXT will develop contents for partners to teach in summer school activities hosted by AZTI (OBAMA-NEXT partner). The summer school will occur every year (usually in June and associated with the World Ocean Day). The summer school is already registered in the database of the European Year of Skills 2023, promoted by the European Commission.

Educational materials derived from the different communication tasks will be merged and organised to a high-education level audience, in the form of five educational modules: (1) data sources and best practices for pelagic habitats (WP2), (2) data sources and best practices for benthic habitats (WP3), (3) user-guide on information products for mapping biodiversity and marine habitats/ecosystems (WP4), (4) case-studies on the use of different marine biodiversity/habitats monitoring and mapping tools (WP5), and (5) relevance of monitoring and mapping tools for decision-makers and implementation of environmental policies (WP6). These outputs will be available in online platforms, such as the EuroGOOS Ocean Literacy platform, and the Ocean Teacher Global Academy (IOC-UNESCO).

5. DEC Impact Assessment

To assess the impact of OBAMA-NEXT, particularly its DEC activities, and the effectiveness of the tasks previously described, several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were established. These KPIs will be regularly monitored together with the periodic reporting, and will be reported in the specific deliverable (D7.7 Impacts of the DEC activities; month 48).

Table 3. Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for the different dissemination (D), exploitation (E), and communication (C) activities.

DEC action	Type of DEC action	KPI	Target
Website	D, C	Number of unique website visitors	2000
Website	D, C	Number of page views	10,000
Twitter	D, C	Number of followers	100
Twitter	D, C	Number of Tweets	200
Twitter	D, C	Number of Tweeter mentions	100
LinkedIn	D, C	Number of connections/followers	100
LinkedIn	D, C	Number of total impressions	4,000
YouTube	C	Number of subscribers	25
YouTube	C	Number of videos posted	10
Videos	D, C	Number of total video views	1,000
Infographics	D, C	Number of social media views (Twitter + LinkedIn)	10,000
Infographics	D, C	Number of social media likes (Twitter + LinkedIn)	500
Infographics	D, C	Number of social media shares (Twitter + LinkedIn)	200
Articles for children	C	Number of engaged schools	5
Articles for children	C	Number of students involved	100
Scientific publications	D	Number of publications associated with the project	100
Scientific conferences	D	Number of presentations/posters	300
Summer schools	D	Number of trainees	150
Join actions, workshops, and meetings	D, E	Number of attendees	200
Policy briefs	D, E	Number of stakeholders reached	100
PAB workshops	D, E	Key stakeholders involved	8
Early Career Researchers	E	Number of PhD/postdocs trained	15
Training workshops with toolbox end-users	E	Number of attendees	100
Educational modules	E	Number of platforms sharing the material	2

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